

**IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF
EMPLOYEES IN THE CONTEXT OF TECHNOLOGICAL
TRANSFORMATION**

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Introduction

In the 21st century, the rapid development of technologies, automation and digitalization pose new challenges for companies. The competitiveness of organizations depends not only on the implementation of innovative technologies, but also on the training of personnel capable of working effectively in such conditions.

Modern studies show that about 70% of companies faced with the introduction of new technologies do not achieve the expected results due to a shortage of qualified specialists. It becomes obvious that the success of companies is associated with the development of employee competencies, such as creativity, digital literacy, leadership skills and adaptability.

The purpose of this work is to study effective methods for managing employee competencies using advanced technologies: virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), digital twins and IoT.

Methods

The following approaches were used for the study:

1. Competency models:

Development and implementation of competency models for various positions. This helps identify key skills and knowledge required to perform specific tasks. Competency models help define the key skills, knowledge, and experience required for

specific positions and tasks. The formula can be expressed as a combination of these factors, where each factor has a certain weight in the overall competency score.

Formula:

$$\text{Competency}_i = w_1 \cdot \text{Skills}_i + w_2 \cdot \text{Knowledge}_i + w_3 \cdot \text{Experience}_i$$

where:

- Skills_i — skill level for task i ,
- Knowledge_i — knowledge level for task i ,
- Experience_i — experience level for task i ,
- w_1, w_2, w_3 — weights representing the importance of each factor.

Example: For an engineer:

- $\text{Skills}_i = 8$ (out of 10),
- $\text{Knowledge}_i = 9$,
- $\text{Experience}_i = 7$.
- Let the weights be $w_1 = 0.4$, $w_2 = 0.3$, and $w_3 = 0.3$.

Then:

$$\text{Competency}_i = 0.4 \cdot 8 + 0.3 \cdot 9 + 0.3 \cdot 7 = 8$$

2. Virtual training:

Using VR and AR to simulate real production processes, teach safe work practices, and practice complex scenarios. The effectiveness of virtual training can be calculated by comparing the training time before and after VR/AR implementation, as well as the reduction in errors.

Formula:

$$\text{VR/AR Effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Time before VR/AR} - \text{Time with VR/AR}}{\text{Time before VR/AR}} \times 100$$

or

$$\text{Error Reduction with VR/AR} = \frac{\text{Errors before VR/AR} - \text{Errors with VR/AR}}{\text{Errors before VR/AR}} \times 100$$

Example:

- Time before VR/AR training: 100 hours,
- Time with VR/AR training: 60 hours.

Effectiveness:

$$\frac{100 - 60}{100} \times 100 = 40\%$$

3. Gamification and mobile platforms:

Using game elements in training and developing mobile applications to increase employee motivation. To measure employee engagement in training through gamification, the following formula can be used:

Formula:

$$\text{Engagement} = \frac{\text{Number of completed courses}}{\text{Number of available courses}} \times 100$$

Example:

If an employee completes 7 out of 10 courses, the engagement will be:

$$\frac{7}{10} \times 100 = 70\%$$

4. Monitoring using IoT:

Installing sensors and other devices to track task completion in real time. This helps identify knowledge gaps and respond quickly. The effectiveness of real-time monitoring with IoT can be calculated by comparing the number of errors before and after implementing IoT.

Formula:

$$\text{IoT Effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Errors before IoT} - \text{Errors with IoT}}{\text{Errors before IoT}} \times 100$$

Example:

- Errors before IoT: 50,
- Errors with IoT: 30.

Effectiveness:

$$\frac{50 - 30}{50} \times 100 = 40\%$$

5. 360-degree method:

Comprehensive assessment of competencies involving managers, colleagues, subordinates, and clients to obtain comprehensive feedback. The 360-degree feedback method involves evaluating competencies from multiple sources (managers, colleagues, subordinates). The average score can be calculated as the mean of all the feedback scores.

Formula:

$$\text{Average Score} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Score}_i}{n}$$

where:

- Score_i — competency score from source i ,
- n — number of sources (e.g., 5 people: manager, colleagues, subordinates).

Example:

If the feedback scores from 5 sources are: 4, 3, 5, 4, 4, the average score will be:

$$\frac{4 + 3 + 5 + 4 + 4}{5} = 4$$

The study was conducted using 10 companies from the industrial and IT sectors that have implemented these methods.

Results

1. Virtual reality and augmented reality:

The implementation of VR/AR has reduced the time for employee training by 40% and reduced the number of errors in production by 25%.

Example: In a company that manufactures chemical equipment, employees practiced actions in emergency situations using VR. This reduced the number of errors in real conditions by 30%.

2. Digital twins:

The use of digital twins has made it possible to test scenarios for changes in employee competencies. For example, in one of the engineering companies, the development of a virtual plant helped reduce training costs by 15% and increase labor productivity by 20%.

3. Gamification:

The development of game-based educational applications has increased employee engagement.

Example: The achievement system in the mobile application motivated 70% of employees to complete courses ahead of schedule.

4. Real-time monitoring:

Using IoT sensors in the workplace has made it possible to quickly record employee errors and automate the issuance of training recommendations.

Discussion

Despite the high efficiency of technologies, their implementation is accompanied by certain difficulties:

1. Employee resistance:

Some employees are not ready for change, fearing that new methods will require additional effort. A motivation program aimed at involving employees in the process can be a solution.

2. High cost of technologies:

Implementation of VR and digital twins requires significant investment. However, the long-term effect (reduced training costs and increased productivity) justifies these costs.

3. Integration issues:

Organizations need to adapt new technologies to existing processes. The solution is gradual implementation with an assessment of intermediate results.

4. Development Prospects:

With the growth of automation, companies will pay more attention to the development of emotional intelligence, leadership skills and the ability to come up with innovative solutions.

Conclusion

Integration of digital technologies into the processes of training and managing employee competencies opens up new horizons for business development. The use of VR, AR, IoT and digital twins ensures not only the safety and effectiveness of training, but also creates conditions for continuous professional growth.

To achieve maximum effect, organizations need to pay attention to:

Development of motivational programs;

Optimization of costs for the implementation of technologies;

Adaptation of new methods to the specifics of each enterprise.

These steps will allow companies to remain competitive in the face of dynamic changes.

References:

Augmented reality in professional training: A review of the literature from 2001 to 2020

X Han, Y Chen, Q Feng, H Luo

Applied Sciences, 2022

Virtual and augmented reality in human resource management and development:

A systematic literature review

P Ferreira, V Meirinhos, AC Rodrigues, A Marques

IBIMA Business Review, 2021•recipp.ipp.pt

Virtual reality as a tool for sustainable training and education of employees in industrial enterprises

V Holuša, M Vaněk, F Beneš, J Švub, P Staša

Sustainability, 2023

Competencies Of A Contemporary Employee In The Age Of Digitalization

GV Petruk, NA Klescheva

European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences, 2021

Artificial intelligence, vr, ar and metaverse technologies for human resources management

O Aydin, E Karaarslan, NG Narin

arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.15383, 2024